

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF VICHARCHIKA W.S.R. TO ECZEMA: A CASE STUDY

Bharat Ganesh Subhashrao^{1*}, Nimmi V.², Sudheer B. R.³

¹Post Graduate Scholar, Dept of PG Studies in Kaumarabhritya, Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India.

²Assistant Professor, Dept of PG Studies in Kaumarabhritya, Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India.

³HOD, Dept of PG Studies in Kaumarabhritya, Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India.

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*Corresponding Author

Bharat Ganesh Subhashrao

Post Graduate Scholar, Dept of PG Studies in Kaumarabhritya, Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India.

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ABSTRACT

Eczema is a reaction pattern manifested by variable clinical and histologic findings. Primary lesions may include papules, erythematous macules and vesicles which can coalesce to form patches and plaques. In severe eczema, secondary lesions such as weeping and crusting may predominate. Eczema has quite resemblance with Vicharchika in Ayurveda. Vicharchika is characterized by skin manifestation having the symptoms Kandu (Itching sensation), Pidika (Papule), Shyava Varna (Blackish brown discoloration) and Bahusrava (Excessive exudation). Case summary: A 10-year-old male patient approached with chief complaints Dry scaly patches of skin over face, upper limbs, lower limbs, abdomen and flanks associated with severe itching since 6 months. The Ayurvedic diagnosis was made as Vicharchika (Eczema) on the basis of signs and symptoms. The patient was given with Ras, Raktha, Mansa Shodhaka and Kushtahara Shamana Aushadis (Oral

medications) along with Parisheka (face & body wash) with Panchavalkala churna kwatha. Later on, Virechana was administered for Koshta Shudhi. From the 2nd day Abhyanga (Oil massage) & Snehapana was started and on 6th day of treatment Virechana was done.

Significant improvement was observed after 07 days of treatment. This case study shows that Ayurvedic treatment is helpful in effective management of Vicharchika and helps in improving the quality of life.

KEYWORDS: Later on, Virechana was administered for Koshta Shudhi.

INTRODUCTION

The skin is the most visible organ of the body and determines to a large extent, our appearance, with a wide function in physical, social and psychological communication. The skin function is hampered with the occurrence of skin diseases. Dermatological problems are seen by pediatricians every day and comprise of around one quarter of a busy outpatient clinic.^[1] In Ayurveda, all types of skin diseases have been discussed under the broad heading Kustha which is further divided as Maha Kustha and Kshudra Kustha. Vicharchika is one of the Kshudra Kustha. According to Acharya Charaka, the skin disease where eruptions over the skin appear with dark pigmentation, itching with profuse discharge from lesion is Vicharchika.^[2] According to Acharya Sushruta severe itching, severe pain and dryness is seen in Vicharchika.^[3] As per Acharya Kashyapa presence of Black, red ulcers with pain, discharges and suppuration over skin is Vicharchika.^[4]

Vicharchika can be compared to eczema. Eczema is noncontagious inflammation of the skin characterized by erythema, scaling, edema, vesiculation and oozing. Eczema, also known as Atopic Dermatitis(AD), involves inflammation of the skin. It is often associated with a family history of atopy (asthma, allergic rhinitis, or eczema). The condition is characterized by scaly or crusty patches of skin, often accompanied by redness, blistering, and itching. Eczema is most common relapsing skin disease seen in infancy and childhood.^[5]

The vitiated three doshas- vata, pitta, kapha along with impaired tvak, rakta, mamsa and ambu together constitute seven essential entities which play role in pathogenesis of this skin disorder and Kapha is the predominant dosha involved in Vicharchika.^[6]

Patient Information

A 10 years old male child visited KB OPD of SSCASR Hospital, Bengaluru on 26/10/25 with complains of diffuse scaly skin lesions over face, upper limbs, lower limbs associated with severe itching, burning sensation & puffiness of face since 6 months. Clinical signs & symptoms like Kandu (itching sensation) Pidika (papule) Shyava Varna (Blackish Brown

discolorations) were present. He had taken treatment from general physician but found no relief, then he came to our hospital for further management.

Associated Complaints: - He had disturbed sleep due to itching & burning sensation.

History of Past illness: - k/c/o Asthma

Family History: - Eczema (mother), photosensitivity to sunlight (father, elder brother)

Developmental History; - All milestones attained at the appropriate age

Immunisation History: - Given as per Schedule up to present age.

Personal History: Diet – Veg, Appetite – Reduced, Bowel – once daily with normal consistency, Micturition – 5-6 times/day, Sleep – Disturbed (due to itching).

General Examination

General condition –fair. T-Afebrile (98f) (Alert, active, well-nourished child with normal sensorium.)

Vital signs - HR – 89/min RR – 20/min

Anthropometry: - Ht – 139 cm, Wt – 30 kg, HC-52 cm, CC-63.2 cm, MAC- 17.6 cm.

Integumentary System Examination: Distribution of the skin lesions was over the face (especially cheeks), thigh, flexural area (forearm, popliteal region, neck). Border ill defined, no sharply demarcated margins. Type of lesion was papules & scaly lesions. The color was brownish associated with rough surface and mild cracking.

Sroto Pariksha: Rasavaha, Raktvaha Srotas.

Symptoms: Kandu (more during night & exposure to sunlight), Daha (burning sensation only after post exposure to sunlight on & off), Pidika (Multiple small, discrete, rough, follicular papules (1–2 mm)/ hyperpigmentation distributed symmetrically on surfaces (upper arms, thighs), cheeks, neck (as in the images), Rukshata - Skin appears dry (xerotic), with coarse texture and fine scaling, some areas show mild erythema/perifollicular redness (suggesting mild inflammation).

Diagnosis: Vicharchika (Atopic Dermatitis)

Therapeutic Intervention

FIRST LINE OF TREATMENT – Day 1- DEEPANA – PACHANA with Chitrakadi vati

SECOND LINE OF TREATMENT – Panchakarma - Snehapana f/b Virechana Karma

Day 2 to 4

Snehapana (intake of ghee prior Virechana karma) was started with Mahatiktaka ghrita in increasing order of 30 ml, 50ml, 50ml for 3 days, once in the early morning with hot water. Breakfast was avoided and light warm diet was advised during Snehapana.

Sarvanga Abhyanga with Panchavalkaladi tailam followed by Bashpa Sweda for 4 days.

Sarvanga dhara with Takra for 4 days

Lepa with Mahatiktakam lepam was given for external application.

Shunthi jala was given for hydration

On Sneha digestion Hingvashtaka churna 1 tsp with warm water before ganji was given.

Panchavalkala churna kwatha for washing face and body was used.

Day 5 – VISHRAMA KAALA: Sarvanga Abhyanga with Panchavalkaladi Kera Tailam followed by Bashpa Sweda done.

Day 6 (31/10/25) – VIRECHANA

SA Panchavalkaladi Kera Tailam f/b Parisheka with Panchavalkala Kwatha Virechana with – Trivrit Lehya – 30 gm was given.

Draksha Kashaya 30 ml given at 09.20 am

Total 12 Vegas passed by patient during Virechana Karma.

It was Madhyama Shuddhi and Madhyama Bala Patient.

Samsarjana Krama for 5 days with 2 Annakala was advised to the Patient.

Shamana Aoushadis [Discharge Medications]

1. Aragwadadi Kashaya – 15ml with 45 ml of water before food morning
2. Dadimadi Ghritam – 1tsp morning empty stomch
3. Manibhadra Gulam – 1tsp at night Afterfood
4. Kaishora guggulu – 1tab – 0 – 1tab afterfood
5. Gandhaka Rasayana - 1tab – 0 – 1tab afterfood
6. Tikthakam Kwatha Tablet - 1tab – 0 – 1tab afterfood

14 days

Outcomes

Parameters	Before Treatment	7 th day of treatment	14 th day of treatment
Kandu (itching sensation)	Present	Reduced	Absent
Pidika (papules)	Present	Reduced	Absent
Shyava varna (brownish discoloration)	Present	Present	Reduced
Srava	Absent	Absent	Absent

DISCUSSION

The Ayurvedic diagnosis was made as Vicharchika (Eczema) on the basis of signs and symptoms. The patient was given with Bashpasweda, Abhyanga (Oil massage), Virechana (Purgation therapy) and Shamana Aushadhis (Oral medications). Chittrakadi Vati for Deepana and Pachana (Ama Pachana)- to stimulate the Agni & helps in the digestion of Amadosha.

Snehapana with Mahatiktakaghrita - As this Mahatiktakaghrita is Tiktapradhana, Pitta-Kaphahara properties. Tikta rasa and Ruksha, Ushna & Laghu guna of the dravyas pacifies Pitta &Kapha – does Srororodhana and Amapachana.

Sarvanga Abhyanga with Panchavalkaladi KeraTaila – Pitta – Kaphashamaka. Vrana-Ropana. Tikta – Kashaya dravyas decrease Itching, dryness and irritation, which are hallmark features of Vicharchika. Used as a Abhyanga, it deeply penetrates into tissues, cleanses toxins(ama), soothes skin, and enhances microcirculation, making it effective for treating Vicharchika by calming skin irritation and supporting tissue repair.

The Swedana Karma is a part of Purvakarma of Panchakarma along with the Snehana Karma. After proper Swedana, it helps the development of Mriduta (Softness), Laghuta (lightness)

and Agnideepti (increase of digestive power) of body. Through Snehana the Dhathus and obstructed Dosha are moistened and on application of Swedana they are mobilized flows towards Koshta and accumulates in Koshta, which are later removed from the body through Shodhana process.

Virechana is useful in in Pitta dominant disorders along with Kapha Sansrista Doshas and Pitta Sthanagata Kapha -: Trivrut Lehya – Mriduvirechana. This reduces the intensity of purgation – making it suitable for Children and Kaphaja disorders.

Parisheka with Panchavalkala Kashaya – Parisheka helps to improving local circulation, inducing sweating to remove toxins, reducing inflammation & pain.

Aragwadhadi Kashaya is Kaphahara, Dahahara and Kandughna. Pancha Tikta Guggulu Gritha is Tikta Rasa, Vata Pittahara, Katu Vipaka, Kapha Vatashamaka and Kandughna. Mahatiktaka Lepa is Vata Pittahara, Dahaghna and Shyavahar. Significant improvements were observed after 07 days of treatment in terms of itching, skin lesion and Shyav varna.

CONCLUSION

Vicharchika (Eczema) is relapsing disease. In present study the patient was given with Bashpa Sweda, Abhyanga (Oil massage), Virechana (Purgation therapy) and Shamana Aushadhis (Oral medications) were found to be effective in the management of Eczema. Present observation and approach definitely boost up the new researcher scholar to manage this condition and do further studies.

Patient Perspective: Patient was satisfied with the treatment in terms of reduced itching, burning sensation, exudation and improved sleep.

Patient Consent: Written permission for the publication of this case study has been obtained from the patient.

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